

A SYSTEMIC FUNCTIONAL MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS (SF-MDA) OF ACADEMIC THEMATIC VISUALS ISSUED BY SCHOOL EDUCATION DEPARTMENT (SED) IN PUNJAB

Rabia Munir^{*1}, Dr. Waqasia Naeem²

^{*1}PhD Scholar, Department of English Applied Linguistics, Minhaj University, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

²Associate Professor Department of English Linguistics, Minhaj University, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

²drwaqasia.eng@mul.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Rabbia

Abstract

This research investigates Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) issued by the School Education Department (SED) in Punjab. Employing Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar within the framework of Multimodal Discourse Analysis as (SF-MDA), it explores how these visuals encode ideational, interpersonal, and textual meanings. It further analysis that how these meanings are visually represented through the elements such as angle, salience, positioning, gaze and roles. The data comprises visuals issued between January to May 2025, sourced from the VocalPakistan website, Education department's official Facebook page, and relevant school's WhatsApp groups. Findings reveal that how (SF-MDA) works to interpret the ethical, social, and moral values through these thematic visuals such as *Speak the Truth*, *Water Conversation*, *Sabar*, *Good Touch Bad Touch*, and *Sharing is Caring*. This study contributes to the field of Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) by demonstrating how visual metafunctions can support educational policymakers in content development and help researchers improve the clarity and communicative impact of academic visuals.

INTRODUCTION

In the age of AI, Academic Discourses and Multimodal texts are running in parallel, as being the part and parcel to each other. This initiative is seemed to be flourished by the School Education Department (SED), as an epitome to spread the ethical considerations through the (MDA). To move on in this direction, the official communication by educational institutions is increasingly seemed to be relied on multimodal resources that combine text, visuals, and spatial arrangements to convey information. Government education departments, particularly in Punjab, are adopting visually rich media to support policy distribution and public engagement. The (SED), a key administrative body overseeing public education, regularly issuing thematic declarations, which are often accompanied by carefully designed

visuals disseminated via social media and digital platforms. These thematic visuals are not merely decorative but are serving as semiotic tools that shape public understanding, perception, and alignment with educational priorities to be achieved on bigger and faster level.

Statement of the Problem

"The problem statement is a clear and concise summary of the research problem, typically contained within one paragraph; its function is to identify the concerned issue" (Ahmad, Farhat & Abbas, 2024). Even though there is the growing stance of visual communication in official educational discourse, but still that access to visual mode of communication is limited in its time span to be introduced in academic orientation. It needs to be worked on that how to

create meanings out of the semiotic mechanisms through the framework of Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). Here, in particular, the thematic declarations issued by SED from January to May, 2025 are of the main concern to be explored and analyzed. The data of this mode found to be circulated informally via social media i.e. WhatsApp mode and it is also observed that, this mode of Visual Commination (VC) is remained under examined in terms of its analysis through the mode of Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). This gap calls for a critical analysis of how visual modes are employed to represent educational themes and shape viewer's engagement.

Research Objectives

- To investigate the representational, interactive, and compositional meanings of academic thematic visuals.
- To explore the metafunction's bridging with multimodality as (SF-MDA).
- To interpret how the integration of visual elements and language in these visuals conveys educational ideologies and pedagogical intent.

Research Questions

1. How representational, interactive, and compositional meanings are constructed in the thematic academic visuals issued by SED?
2. How do the metafunctions integrate with multimodality to reflect the core themes of SED's monthly educational declarations, according to SF-MDA?
3. To what extent do the multimodal resources (e.g., imagery, layout, color, gaze, and salience) in these visuals support SED's discourse on students' moral upbringing and educational values?

Significance of the Study

The present research contributes to the up brining of multimodal discourse analysis in the field of academic visual communication within a governmental educational context of the Punjab. By analyzing how thematic visuals convey meaning beyond their accompanying texts, the research offers an insights into the broader semiotic strategies used in the department of Education of public-sector. It also bridges the gap

between formal document analysis and the informal on the part of the interpretations made by the audience. Significantly, the particular Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) are observed, explored and the analysis would work to interpret, explain and highlight their interconnectivity within the visual and to the pedagogical concerns as well. This interconnectivity would not only be highlighted in between the text and images, but most importantly, this connection is going to be explored in terms of the bilinguality too as found in the visuals.

This research would contribute in presenting the Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) as readable through the lens of Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). These findings would have implications for, educators and media designers seeking to enhance clarity, inclusivity, and effectiveness in public practices.

Literature Review

"Review of the literature summarize and evaluate the text of writing of the definite theme, and provide frame work to think about the possible consequence of innovative study" (Ahmad et al., 2023, p,2). "A review of literature may only be a clear overview of the sources, in an organizational pattern, and its function is to estimate and summarize the previous writings linked to current topic" (Ahmad et al., 2024, p,3). The incorporation of visual semiotics into institutional communication has become increasingly significant in educational contexts. This part is being playing a pivotal role in the academic initiatives made by (SED) in the Punjab Schools. An umbrella term, which falls under this category, is shared in discourse by the scholars such as Kress and van Leeuwen (2006), who argue that visuals are not merely illustrative but also play a central role in constructing meaning, particularly when combined with text in multimodal formats. Their seminal work, *Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design*, provides a foundational framework for understanding how elements such as gaze, color, modality, and layout in whole tend to occupy multiple interpretations in single image.

Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) as being bridging an interaction between different modes of communication serves as a dialectical process. The process which offers a perspective that how meanings from the visuals are generated on the

basis of the interpretations made on the basis of the context. It also offers a robust framework for understanding how meaning is constructed not only through language but also through a variety of semiotic modes such as image, color, layout, and gesture. This review synthesizes key contributions to the field, by incorporating Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) as a tool to interpret the visuals under the impact of AI.

On the part of the multimodality (Kress and Bezemer, 2023) claim that multimodality is a domain, where semiotics are being identified and where their meanings are being shaped. They identified this domain as being an embodiment and reflection of multi-modes of communication. And for the viewers it serves as a complex system of signs, of which they create meanings on the basis of their interpretations. In their book, *Multimodal Discourse Analysis*, they provide a comprehensive theoretical grounding of (MDA) by addressing the ambiguity surrounding the term "discourse" and proposing multimodality as an analytical domain that recognizes language as just one among many semiotic resources. However, their discussion remains abstract and may require contextual adaptation when applied to concrete visual education campaigns.

On the other hand, in her work (Luca, 2020) presents the applicability of the theoretical framework to media content. Her approach stresses the ideological role of visuals in institutional messaging. Similar to this, (O'Halloran, 2008), made an investigation of the ideational meanings of the printed text, through the application of Systemic Functional (SF) approach to Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA). For this purpose, she used the cross-functional system in the form of color and made the analysis of the written, printed and electronic texts through the application of image-editing software to conduct detailed ideological analysis on an intersemiotic level.

Moreover, on the part of the multimodality (Jewitt, Bezemer and O'Halloran 2016) contribute by providing an accessible methodological guide that how to conduct a multimodal research. For this purpose, they outline systematic procedures such as developing research questions, data collection, and visual transcription. However, the book focuses more on practical application and less on advanced theoretical debates.

Apart from the other writings, (Kress and van Leeuwen 2014) work on the single feature of the visuals composition, which is color. Here, they tackle this feature as a composed constitute of grammar which is complete in itself to generate the meaning. They posit the color as a semiotic mode with its own grammatical structure. However, the article primarily focuses on color in isolation, without extensively addressing its interaction with other modes such as text or imagery. On the other hand, (Van Leeuwen, 2021) extends the boundaries of multimodality by presenting movement and mobility as semiotic resources. Apart from the above mentioned researches he sets a different parameter in the field of research by presenting a framework that is more applicable to dynamic visual forms such as animated videos or classroom recordings.

Further, (Van Leeuwen, 2017) presents a dialectical relation between the image features and their interpretations on the part of the ideological interpretations which are rooted in social contexts. He highlights this phenomenon by claiming that visual composition is governed by social norms and ideologies. He claims that commonly visuals constitutes are influenced by normative discourses rooted in social class and institutional messaging. In this research this framework of Leeuwen is especially relevant for analyzing how (SED) visuals reproduce or challenge dominant narratives around education, gender, and identity through compositional choices such as layout and symbol placement.

Meanwhile, visual communication in the field of education is frequently being employed in policy promotion, classroom instruction, and public engagement strategies. In the field of education, (Bezemer and Jewitt (2010), have highlighted the complex interactions between the basic constituents (each of which contributed to the elaboration of meaning) of the images. And this attempt of them has been elaborated in the form of multimodal analysis. Similarly, in the field of School Education (Serafini, 2014), has also highlighted the interpretations as being derived out of the visual semiotics through the lens of multimodality.

Moreover, (Jones, 2017) also claimed that, on the part of the educational bodies, there is a great inclination towards the implication of visual strategies to make more effectiveness of the meanings out of the context. (Rashid and

Mukhtar, 2020) are also of the same view that, as being dealing with the variety of literacy levels, visuals are of a perfect model to make more feasible interpretations of them across diverse linguistic and social groups

Identification of Gaps in Existing Literature

This research is different from the earlier literature as it serves an invocation to the emergence of Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) Initiatives as an unexplored mode of communication. Despite being exploring the applicability of multimodal strategies and being investigating the impacts of multimodal analysis in variety of researches, there still lies a big gap. This gap is multi-oriented which can be elaborated on different levels which include:

- Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) Initiatives taken by **School Education Department (SED)**
- Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA),
- Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA)

"This gap is especially noteworthy in considering that the School Education Department (SED) by Punjab is regularly issuing monthly thematic visuals to communicate ethical values and moral objectives in public schools. These visuals typically feature official text messages (in bilingual, English and Urdu text forms) as accompanied by visuals created to build a relationship between the authority, teacher, student and parents.

Despite this, the meaning-making capacity of these visuals, that how they convey messages and connect with different audiences is not thoroughly examined earlier. Moreover, there is a lack of in-depth multimodal research that combines Systemic Functional and Multimodal Analysis (MDA) approaches to analyze such content in the context of Pakistan's education discourse system.

Theoretical Framework

The structure that can support a theory is called theoretical framework (Arshad, Mehmood & Ahmad, 2025; Yousaf et al., 2025). This study is grounded in key theoretical perspectives, primarily drawing on the principles of Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). Developed by (Kress and Van Leeuwen 2006), (SF-MDA) provides a systematic approach to understanding how images communicate

meaning in ways analogous to the language. Core visual components, such as color, composition, gaze, salience, and framing are organized to engender culturally and socially recognizable meanings.

(Kress and van Leeuwen, 2006) outline that images function through three interconnected structures: the representational (ideational), interactive (interpersonal), and compositional (textual) metafunctions. This creates an accommodation with Halliday's linguistic metafunctions, offering an inclusive framework for analyzing how visual constitutes, operates and derive meanings within social and communicative contexts.

In the context of educational and governmental discourse, Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) serves as a critical tool for examining how imagery, comprising portrayals of political figures, national symbols, and pedagogical themes conveys messages related to power, legitimacy, morality, and national identity (Machin, 2007).

Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA)

This research applies Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) to better understand how communication works when it combines different modes of meaning, like words, images, layout, and even gestures. Instead of just analyzing the text (MDA) looks at how all these features work together to create meaning.

O'Halloran (2008) elaborates that (MDA), guides in to see how different forms of communications merge to create a clearer, more powerful message, especially in formal or public contexts. Jewitt (2009) also emphasizes that meaning is rarely communicated through words or images alone. In educational settings, for example, visuals often mix ideas about politics, culture, and teaching to express deeper messages.

Jones (2009), builds on Carey Jewitt's idea of "sites of display," showing that meaning doesn't come just from the image or message itself, but also from where and how it's presented. For instance, something shown in a book might be understood differently than the same thing shown on a screen. Using Scollon's term "a watch," Jones highlights how viewing visuals is a social act that is shaped by the context and audience. The text also critiques the idea that images have fixed "affordances" (or uses), pointing out that their meaning depends on

how and where they're used. While the analysis is rich in theory, it could benefit from more real-life examples in education or digital media to make it easier to apply.

In this regard, (Bateman's, (2014) introductory textbook presents a detailed overview of multimodality, focusing on how text and image work together across disciplines. Bateman examines a range of theoretical approaches, including socio-semiotics, visual communication, psycholinguistics, rhetorical analysis, and cognitive metaphor theory, underlining their applications to materials such as advertisements, picture books, comics, and textbooks. The book evaluates each framework through practical examples and encourages critical inquiry through targeted research questions. Accessible to newcomers, it serves as a key resource for students in linguistics, media, and visual studies exploring the interaction between visual and verbal modes.

Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA)

Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) is based on Halliday's theory of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and is useful for analyzing how visuals and other modes work together to create meaning. This approach looks at three main ways of how meaning is made:

- **Ideational:** how experiences or ideas are shown
- **Interpersonal:** how relationships and feelings are built
- **Textual:** how everything is organized to make sense as a whole

In educational visual semiotics, for instance, posters about "Sabar" (patience) or "Good Touch & Bad Touch" (SF-MDA) helps to show how meaning is created through images, both in terms of the messages they carry and how they connect with the viewer. Unsworth and Cleirigh (2014) pointed out that those images in education are not just add-ons; they play an important role in teaching and shaping beliefs.

This framework is especially helpful in understanding how the School Education Department (SED) uses Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) to promote these themes, spread moral values, and national identity by carefully designing images to deliver and practice powerful messages in educational grounds.

While many studies have used Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA), or a combination of (MDA) with (SF-MDA), to analyze things like advertisements, picture books, comics, and textbooks using various visual theories, but still there is a gap when it comes to applying these methods to Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) created by the School Education Department (SED) in Punjab, Pakistan.

This research helps to fill that gap by applying Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) framework on selected Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs). This approach is especially useful for analyzing how these visuals, shared by the Punjab government, are designed to promote certain values and ethical messages to students.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the part of the research study in which researchers give an account of the research methods, which they have used to conduct their research (Rao et al., 2023; Sadaf et al., 2024; Arshad, ahmad & zafar, 2025). This research uses a **qualitative research design**, based on Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) and **social semiotics**. A qualitative approach is helpful because it focuses on how audience understands and creates meaning through both the text and visuals in a specific social and cultural setting (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). This design allows for a close look at how images are built, what they aim to communicate, and the deeper ideas or messages they carry, especially in educational materials.

Data Sources and Materials

The data includes **Official Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) and notifications** as being shared by the **School Education Department (SED) Punjab, Pakistan**, from **January to May 2025**. These were collected from:

- The (SED)'s official website: The (SED)'s official **Facebook page**
- **Posters and banners** shared in school-related **WhatsApp groups**

These materials were chosen because they reflect monthly themes like *Speak the Truth, Stop Bullying, Save Water, Sabar and Gratitude, Good Touch Vs Bad Touch, Leadership and Sharing is Caring* that are promoted in public elementary schools as being a constitute of both words and visuals.

Data Collection Methods

The research used **purposive sampling**, mainly five visuals or notifications were chosen: one from each month. The visuals were selected based on:

- Whether both the text and image were available
- How clearly the visuals matched that month's theme
- Whether they were easily accessible from official or widely-used platforms

Each visual was collected and labeled by month and theme. Information like the **date, platform used** and any extra **explanatory text** was also recorded to give more background on each image.

Analytical Procedures

The visuals were studied using a **two-step multimodal analysis (MDA, SF-MDA)**.

Theo van Leeuwen's Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) (2005, 2021) is used to examine key design features like:

- **Salience** (what stands out)
- **Framing** (how elements are placed)
- **Gaze, vectors, color, and composition**

These helped to identify the roles of the people or symbols shown, how they connect with viewers, and how everything is organized visually.

1. **Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA)** based on **Halliday's three metafunctions** (1978): It was used to understand:

- **What is shown** (ideational meaning)
- **How it engages the viewer** (interpersonal meaning)
- **How it's arranged to make sense** (textual meaning)

Each visual was interpreted in relation to its **cultural, educational, and political background**,

focusing on how the visuals support official messages and shape behaviors in schools.

Justification for Methodological Choices

Applying a **qualitative multimodal approach** fits to this research's goal: to explore how meanings are visually built in official school campaigns. Multimodal analysis digs deeper into how visuals **express hidden messages, values, and social ideas** (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006).

The combined application of the theories of **Halliday** and **KressVan Leeuwen** helps to interpret the institutional messages in whole. This approach has been widely used in educational and policy research and particularly here for exploring how visuals work in the **School Education Department's communication**.

Data Analysis

This research investigates the Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) issued by the School Education Department (SED) from January to May, 2025 using a combination of traditional and modern methods to understand how these visuals communicate meaning.

It used Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) and Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) in combined form to study each visual from three angles: what the visual shows (distance, relation, interaction), how it emotionally connects with the viewers (distance, angle and gaze through eye contact, figure placement, or focus), and how (pattern, layout and gaze) helps to convey the message clearly. It is also applied to identify key elements like color, framing, and direction to analyze their impact in meaning making. The viewer (teachers, students, parents) and platforms (like Facebook and WhatsApp) are also considered to make the interpretations on the basis of the context. Overall, the study shows that how these visuals as being issued by (SED), considerably the amalgamation of visuals and texts essentially are in need to be analyzed through the lens of (SF-MDA), to explore the hidden metafunctions in them. These visuals are analyzed below as:

MOST IMPORTANT

No. SO(A-1)2-2/2024
GOVERNMENT OF THE PUNJAB
SCHOOL EDUCATION DEPARTMENT
 Dated Lahore, the 31st December, 2024

To: **All Chief Executive Officers (DEA) in the Punjab.**

Subject: **THEME OF THE MONTH OF JANUARY 2025 = "TO SPEAK THE TRUTH" (سچ بولنا)**

Chief Executive Officer
 Dairry No. 57
 03/01/25
 School Education Authority Punjab

Kindly refer to the subject captioned above.

2. I am directed to state that to promote honesty, integrity and transparency in Schools, encouraging students to speak the truth and upholding moral values, whereby Competent Authority has declared the theme of the month of January, 2025 as "TO SPEAK THE TRUTH" (سچ بولنا). To celebrate this theme, following activities and events in public schools across Punjab shall be arranged by involving parents, teachers and community members promoting a collaborative effort to ensure the values of truthfulness in our students:

SR. NO.	DATE	ACTIVITIES	DETAILS
1.	13.01.2025 to 17.01.2025	Importance of Truth in Islam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Host classroom discussions on "Truth as a Divine Command" "Truth as a Trait of Prophets"
		Storytelling Sessions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize sessions where teachers or guest speakers share stories emphasizing the importance of truthfulness. Each participant contributes one truthful sentence to build a story collectively.
		Truth Telling Circle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants sit in a circle and each person takes a turn sharing a truthful experience, thought, or feeling.
		Game on truthfulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create scenarios where participants must decide how to respond truthfully (e.g. "What would you say if you broke something valuable?")
		School Assemblies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicate assemblies to the theme of truth, where students can present skits, speeches, or poems that reinforce the message of truthfulness.
		Recognition Programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish programs that recognize and reward truth behavior among students. Students may be encouraged to reinforce the value of truth in the school community.
2.	20.01.2025 to 24.01.2025	Role-playing Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage students to participate in role-playing scenarios that highlight situations requiring truthfulness. This interactive approach helps them understand the value of truth in real-life contexts.

CS CamScanner

SR. NO.	DATE	ACTIVITIES	DETAILS
		Debate Competitions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host debates on topics related to truth. • "Benefits of speaking the truth". • "Truth builds trust in society".
3.	27.01.2025 to 31.01.2025	Creative Writing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essay writing competition on the importance of truthfulness. • Assign essays or short stories where students explore themes of truthfulness. • Enabling them to reflect on the significance of truth in personal and societal segments.
		Art Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students create posters or drawings that depict the value of truth.

3. I am further directed to request you to ensure that all schools in your district participate in these activities and celebrate the theme of the month with enthusiasm and fervor. A consolidated weekly report must be furnished at the end of week including pictorial evidences of all activities / tasks to this department via e-mail soacademic1@gmail.com and WhatsApp groups.

4. This may be treated as MOST IMPORTANT.

SECTION OFFICER (ACAD-I)

CC:

1. Director Public Instruction (SE/EE) Punjab, Lahore with the request to liaison with CEOs and ensure compliance of above instructions in letter & spirit.
2. Deputy Director (Monitoring), School Education Department.
3. PSO to Senior Minister Punjab, 8th Club, Lahore.
4. PS to Minister, School Education Department.
5. PS to Secretary School Education Department.
6. PS to Special Secretary, School Education Department.
7. PS to Additional Secretary (General), School Education Department.
8. PA to Deputy Secretary (Acad), School Education Department.

Office of the Chief Executive Officer (DEA) Gujranwala.

Endt. No 05 /G.I

Dated 03-01- /2025

Forwarded in original to all DEOs (SE, M/F-EE) in district Gujranwala for necessary compliance under intimation to this office.

Assistant Director (General)
For Chief Executive Officer
(DEA) Gujranwala.

03/01/2025

CS CamScanner

On the part of the analysis of the above attached notification, besides being composed of the text it also embodies certain visual elements. These visual elements are firstly, getting disclosed through three stamps which are visualized at the different angles. First stamp visual of the Govt of Punjab is presented at the top-left high position. The close shot of the stamp is representing that the visual is taken from the frontal angle. This capturing of the visual from the frontal angle is reflecting that the relation between the viewer and the representation is the relation of power. This stamp with the symbol of Moon and star is representing the cultural identity of the Pakistan. The positions, the angle, the symbols in the stamp, the food items, under the stamp represented through the front angle all are signifying the concept of authority and particularly the power.

Besides that, second stamp visual, over the statement with text constituents (entitled as Chief Executive Officer) date and diary # is also reflecting the impact of power. Besides this the right-above -mid position and frontal display of this visual is also representing the relation of being authoritative and dominance.

Meanwhile, the third stamp is posted with different title as: Assistant Director (General). The position where it is visualized is the right-bottom position. The representation of stamp at the down position is an expression of the relation of low rank of this official (General) than the above mentioned high rank officials (Punjab Govt and CEO).

In addition to this the stamps in visuals is also composed of other features which would be analyzed under the heading of (MDA). It includes: layout, columns, sr#, categories of the events alongside the text (as being relevant to theme) and the mentioning of the dates as a time limit for the completion of this task, all of these are also represented through the lens of (SF-MDA) too. The organized representation of the above mentioned visual features are reflecting that the relation between the viewer and the represented aspects is like of the agent and the patient.

Moreover, the formwork of (MDA) not only explored the visual features, rather it also worked to analyze the inclusion of Urdu text سچ بولنا in the visuals as representing the cultural aspect of the discourse.

Furthermore, the framework of (SF-MDA) it is also highlighting the ranking of officials (high and low). Official's discourse (stamps and text) order and the organized arrangements of the all the categories within fixed time-frame are setting the officials at high rank who are in a position to issue orders and make them obligatory for the viewers to follow and oblige them.

Meanwhile Kress and van Leeuwen's (2008) framework Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) tends to analyze the visual under the headings which include: Representational Meaning: as being reflecting the authority and institutional endorsement through the official stamps, and formal layout. Further on the interactive mode of meaning the seal and handwritten annotations simulate interaction and give a sense of urgency, importance, and real-time involvement.

On the level of interdiscursivity the document blends: religious, educational (structured learning activities) and civic discourse (community building, integrity in school environments). And on the part of institutional framing it explores the positions and angles of all of the three visuals as right-top, top-mid and bottom-right are reflecting the relation and differentiation of the designations of the officials, which is just explored and analyzed through the module of (MDA). And on the part of the (SF) this visual has reflected the ideational (representative of the visual elements made above), interaction (as reflecting the relation of power through visual representation) and compositional elements (distance, angle, position and relation of the visual elements expressed above). So, this visual is representing the relation between the participants as some of them as high in power and other as the low in power, who have to oblige the message within the given time frame. Furthermore, Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) works on the semiotic resources in the form of bold text, underlines, tables, and official stamps, which convey seriousness, urgency, and authority. Here the dates and structured columns act as temporal and instructional semiotic tools, guiding implementation in schools. It further works on to reflect: which promotes the cultural and religious ideology. Additionally, on social grounds students are positioned as learners and moral subjects. Teachers and administrators are presented as facilitators.

In a nutshell this whole analysis can be summed up as in

Theme of the month
February 2025
Water Conservation

پانی کے تحفظ کے پوسٹرز
(10-02-2025 - 14.02.2025)

- پوسٹرز، بینرز اور نعرے جیسے "محفوظ پانی"، "محفوظ زندگی" یا "بر قطرہ قیمتی ہے،" بوند بوند زندگی کے ذریعے آگاہی پھیلاؤ
- طلبہ سے وعدہ لینا کہ وہ پانی بچانے کی عادات اپنائیں گے۔
- طلبہ کو گھروں میں نل چیک کرنے اور پانی کے رساؤ کی نشان دہی کا کام دینا۔
- طلبہ کو پانی کے استعمال کے طریقوں پر سروے کرنے کی حوصلہ افزائی کرنا

پانی کے استعمال کو روکنا
(03-02-2025 - 07.02.2025)

- طلبہ کو پانی کے تحفظ کی اہمیت کے بارے میں آگاہ کرنا۔
- طلبہ اپنے پانی کے استعمال کا سالانہ تخمینہ لگائیں اور کلاس میں بتائیں۔
- پانی کے بچاؤ کی عادات کو فروغ دینا (مثلاً برش کرنے وقت نل بند کرنا)
- پانی کے تحفظ پر آگاہی کے سیشنز کا انعقاد کرنا

پانی کے استعمال کا سروے
(17-02-2025 - 21.02.2025)

- پانی کے تحفظ کے ماہرین کو لیکچرز کے لیے مدعو کرنا۔
- طلبہ کو پانی کے تحفظ کے طریقے سکھانا۔
- طلبہ کو پانی کے تحفظ کے موضوعات پر آرٹ پروجیکٹس بنانے کی ترغیب دینا

مضمون نویسی مقابلات
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- پانی کے غیر ضروری استعمال کو روکنے کے موضوع پر مباحثے اور مضمون نویسی کا مقابلے منعقد کرنا۔
- پانی کی قلت اور اس کے ماحولیاتی اثرات پر لیکچرز کا اہتمام۔
- پانی کے تحفظ اور اسے بچانے کے طریقوں پر کوئز مقابلے منعقد کرنا

چیف ایگزیکٹو آفیسر ڈسٹرکٹ ایجوکیشن اتھارٹی گوجرانوالہ

The above mentioned visual alongside Urdu and English texts, presents the official individuals as the figures in authority, which is being manifested through the top representation of them in the visual. The visual is comprises of certain Systematic Functional Analysis (SFL) elements, and (SF-MDA) covers angle, distance, interaction, gaze, and cultural signs. Here, the woman's dupatta and dress is also picturing a cultural sign. Her hand's posture is a reflection of her in-depth integrity, and of making a promise (with the viewer). Besides that, the educational figure beside the woman is also visualized through the front angle and close shot as being familiar to each other. This familiarization is reflected through the sameness of their poses.

As making an attempt to analyze the above mentioned visual, it further elaborates that the facial expressions of the authoritative figures are strongly highlighting their willingness and integrity. The man in authority's expressions are also presenting that yes, they have delivered their message through the thematic visuals. Other aspects of (MDA) as the calendar layout and headings represent educational and institutional intent. The figures serve as vectors to guide attention, creating a narrative about authority, instruction, and awareness. Direct gazes

(especially from the two individuals at the top) create engagement, interaction and equality. Frontal angle suggests equality and openness; eye-level positioning reduces hierarchy and promotes approachability. And the salience is given to the people at the top (authoritative), supported by large fonts and color contrast in text (especially the red and blue themes).

The compositional meaning, which is analyzed here, is this that the visual is spatially organized, categorizing and sequencing different activities according to dates. Boxing of texts in bullet style is indicating the categorization and clarity of particular action.

The logo on the top left side of the visual is reflection of the background of the message that the notification or the visual is being issued especially by the Govt. of the Punjab. The green color of the logo is presenting a visual of main economic source on the background of this visual, who wants its implementations to be made sure. Multimodal Discourse Analysis (MDA) covers the language the usage of Bilingual texts targets a broad audience. English serves as an official/globalized anchor ("Theme of the Month"), while Urdu contextualizes its locality. Kress's view of interaction is highlighted through the repetition of keywords like "پانی" (water), "تحفظ"

(conservation), and "طلبہ" (students) as showing an interaction with the viewers.

Besides that interdiscursivity can best be elaborated through the integration of certain elements which include the discourses of: governance (government logos, official portraits), education (mention of students, poster/essay activities) and environmentalism (theme of water conservation).

Moreover, institutional tone is providing specific directives for student engagement. And this

institutional validity is constructed via official photos, logo, and precise dates.

Additionally, Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) is also used to explore the semiotic resources. As the visuals and portrayal of leaders evokes ethos; communicates authority, trust, and alignment with state narrative. And the layout covers as being planned by the administrative in an organized order.

This visual is a composition of the features, which Kress and van Leeuwen termed as Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). This model tends to highlight the distance, gaze and angle of its constituents. The top-left visual of the officials as being closer to each other is the reflection of the aspect that they are not strangers to each other. Their representation at the top-left angle is reflecting their position of power and authority. The gaze of both of these officials is representing the two different aspects. The gaze of the official (woman) at the top, as being directed to the (unseen) public is setting the visual as direct eye-engagement with that particular viewer. While the gaze of the man at top: as eyes' being directly catching the (camera) lens is reflecting the aspect of equality in relation with the viewer. While the gaze of child from above the viewer, is representing the reflection, curiosity, and being the attendee. On the part of

the narrative structures, child's gaze towards above mentioned thematic highlights (verse) is reflecting the aspect of accommodation as being the goal of the higher authorities was. The use of Urdu words and wearing of dupatta are making the cultural representations. The man in traditional dress is prominently placed and visually highlighted, possibly representing authority or leadership. While, the high color saturation, formal dress, and facial expressions suggest seriousness and official tone on the part of the authority. The western-style calendar clearly highlights the time fixed for making an exposure of this theme to the relevant audience.

Under the heading of Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA), this visual covers the features which would be analyzed as Modes, which include: Linguistic (Urdu, Arabic, English), visual (photos, text layout, colors) and typographic (fonts differentiate levels

of authority). As for the matter of intertextuality falls, it concerns to highlight that how the Arabic text is interwoven with Urdu translation, signaling cultural-religious identity. Moreover, Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) also explores the cultural semiotics by presenting the outlooks of different cultures. The visuals of political figures on the top left suggest their institutional endorsement. And the visual of the man on right is reflecting as the official in rank lower than the represented above. His gaze as being directing towards the (unseen) audience and opposite to the viewer (lens) reflects his lesser control as compared to the above mentioned official.

Furthermore, by using Halliday's three metafunctions the visual would be analyzed under the headings which include: ideational

metafunctions (which is also reflected through the gazes of the authority), interpersonal metafunctions along with analyzing the eye contact of all of the four figures in the picture.

And on the part of the textual metafunctions it covers the integration between the visuals and the texts in a very organized way. Making an interpretations from the top left to right and from the top to bottom the visual is analyzed from all the sides of it as being reflecting a textual interaction as being an essential feature of its structure as cohesive structure.

The sameness of the poses of the figures in the visual, represent the harmonized and integrated layout which tends to highlight an interaction between the text and visuals as a guide to reading path from top to bottom and from left to right.

The above referred visual, comprises of the elements of the Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). These elements are analyzed here through the gazes of the officials at the top corners. This reflection of them at the top corners is showing the authoritative positions of them. Here, the gazes, gestures and facial expressions of the both of these authoritative figures are making an eye-contact with the viewer, which is reflecting the level of equality between them. And their gazes are shown

as directly addressing the audience as being delivered

their message through the visual. The visual is taken from the front angle and highlighting the impact of interaction. While, sameness of the poses is also adding to reflect the impact of harmonization in the visual. Another element of Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA), is wearing of dupatta and the waistcoat which are presenting the cultural aspects. Besides that the topic layout and its text are representing the cohesiveness of the pattern.

Meanwhile, the mentioning of the dates represents the fixation of the time and the textual representation of the different levels of the competitions is adding to the compositional aspect of Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA).

As for the matter of narrative representation is considered, it concerns to reflect that the phrase "Good Touch and Bad Touch" is of the main concern. The gazes are adding to the elaboration of their cultural integrity and particularly their authoritative status. The visual is also displaying

the different font styles which help to separate the topic, schedule, and endorsements, giving it a formal, official tone.

Additionally, Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) makes an analysis of the modes which includes: language (as the visual is marked with bilinguality, mainly Urdu, and English terms like "Good Touch and Bad Touch", visuals: political figures and the layout. The design flows from top to bottom, from authoritative figures to the topic.

Here Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA), makes the possibility of reading or the interpretations of the visuals which is the major contribution of this research.

It makes an analysis of the visuals on these levels: Two key figures are shown as being the representative of authority and trust.

Someone is holding the blocks, likely a child tends to show the interaction with the viewer and to make the message feel more real and active.

The people in the visual look directly at the audience; this direct eye contact invites attention, engagement and interaction.

The camera shows them up close, this gives the aspect of approachability. Angle of the photo highlights the aspect of equality to the people shown. Realistic photos, clear visuals and official

logos make the whole thing feel serious and trustworthy.

The visual carries the Systematic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) features such as: top part, logo and faces show the authority. It would recognize faces, read text (like "May 2025"), and identify objects like the blocks and logos. It would see the blocks as the main focus based on their placement.

Besides that, Systematic Functional Multimodal Analysis (SF-MDA) looks at how different elements (visuals, words, layout) work together to create meaning. Here, the visual covers the faces, blocks, and symbols, languages (English and Urdu) and the design (way that how everything is arranged), the interpretations of all of them making the visuals readable.

Conclusion

This research worked to analyze and elaborate the Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) Initiatives made by the School Education Department (SED). These visuals have been analyzed through the lens of (SF-MDA) as all four categories being linked with each other in making the interpretations of the given visuals in three basic dimensions of metafunctions. This would also work to fill the gap of viewing the whole constitutes as thematic visuals on a single platform. Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA) shows how different elements like text and visuals work together to create a composed meaning, including emotional and social ones. Moreover, the role of visuals in Academic grounds also serving as a mode of interaction in the square relationship of (authority-teacher- student and parents). So, this research would work to dig, dive, explore, highlight and analyze the meanings out of those Academic Thematic Visuals (ATVs) as being observed under the shadow of Systemic Functional Multimodal Discourse Analysis (SF-MDA). Together, these methods offer a clear way to study how educational visuals are not just decorative, but actually reflect and spread bigger ideas about society, values, and politics and about social practices.

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